

Alignment of Teeth by Driftodontics: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Physiological tooth movement or driftodontics of teeth in extraction space decrease the amount of mechanotherapy during clinical orthodontics. This is especially helpful in young patients with anterior mandibular crowding. We present a case of 13-year-old girl with severe crowding in the lower arch and moderate crowding in the upper arch. Anterior crowding in mandibular arch was relieved by driftodontics after extraction of first premolars and placement of lingual arch to prevent molar mesialization.

Keywords: *Driftodontics, Crowding, Extraction*

INTRODUCTION

Driftodontics is defined as timely removal of teeth to enable spontaneous eruption and alignment of neighboring teeth without application of any traction force.¹ Driftodontics is based on the fact that in presence of normal lip and tongue muscle tone, mandibular anterior teeth tend to move distal into extraction space while there is little mesial movement of posterior teeth.² Driftodontics is mostly not indicated for maxillary arch as little lingual movement of maxillary incisors occur with driftodontics. This physiological drift of teeth is a part of many important treatment modalities in clinical orthodontics such as development of dentition by extracting deciduous teeth, serial extractions and premolars extraction in early permanent dentition. This physiological tooth movement was first put forward by Bourdet.³

Driftodontics occur because of the pull of transseptal fibers. These transseptal fibers stabilizes the teeth against separating forces.⁴ As natural tooth movement is involved in driftodontics less relapse is anticipated. It is a well-established fact in orthodontics that there is more relapse of lower incisors than upper incisors. Thus, movement of the lower incisors by driftodontics will lead to less relapse. Moreover, orthodontic brackets accumulate more plaque leading to greater chances of enamel demineralization, dental caries and periodontal issues. As less mechanotherapy is involved to relieve incisor crowding and to move of canine distally resulting in less root resorption which is associated with orthodontic treatment. Other purposed benefits include stable occlusion, short therapy with fixed appliances and increased dentoalveolar support.^{1,3}

Driftodontics is advised for class I and II malocclusion cases. Class II division I malocclusion is commonly

encountered in Asian population with higher incidence in females than male population.⁵ To decrease prominence of incisors and relieve crowding if any, space needs to be gained in arch either by extraction of premolars or distalization of whole arch. We present a case of severe mandibular anterior crowding which was treated with premolar extractions and driftodontics.

DIAGNOSTIC SUMMARY

A 13 years 2 months old female presented with chief complaint of prominent upper incisors and crooked upper and lower teeth. Her profile was convex and frontal view was symmetric (figure no. 1). Molar relationship was class I bilaterally with a Class II incisor relationship and overjet was 6 mm, while overbite was 55% (figure no. 1). Upper and lower dental midlines were shifted to the left by 3 mm when compared with facial midline. There was moderate crowding in upper arch, severe crowding in lower arch and labially ectopic maxillary canine on left side. There was no other significant finding or pathology.

The cephalometric analysis showed a mild skeletal Class II jaw-base relationship (ANB, 5°) (Table no. 1). The mandibular plane was steep (SN-Mand, 40°). There was bimaxillary dento-alveolar proclination. As a result, the interincisal angle was decreased (113°). Lips were competent at rest. Lower lip was protrusive and nasolabial angle was acute.

TREATMENT OBJECTIVES

- (1) Retrusion of upper incisors and relieve crowding to address patient's chief complaint.
- (2) Level, align and coordinate the upper and lower arch.
- (3) Correct inter-arch relationships achieving a class I incisor, canine and maintain class I Molar relationship with mutually protected functional

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- occlusion.
- (4) Achieve an attractive smile and balanced facial profile
- (5) Retain corrected results.

TREATMENT PLAN

To relieve crowding in upper and lower arch, shift midline to the right side and for correction of overjet, all first premolars extraction plan was implemented. Written informed consent was obtained from the patient's guardians.

TREATMENT PROGRESS

Bands for upper and lower first molars were selected and impression was taken with bands for fabrication of nance appliance in upper arch and lingual holding arch in lower jaw for maintenance of posterior anchorage.

After extraction, appliances were cemented. Upper and lower teeth were left to move physiologically by driftodontics in premolar extraction space.

After 3 months into treatment, an upper fixed appliance (0.022" x 0.028" slot) with MBT prescription was bonded and 0.016" Nickel titanium (NiTi) wire was ligated.

0.019"x0.025" stainless steel (SS) wire was placed after 6 month of treatment and canine retraction was started in upper arch. Improvement in lower arch

crowding was also observed by physiologic drift of teeth.

Nance was removed after upper canine retraction was completed. Incisor retraction of upper 4 anteriors was started with class I elastic of 1/8" delivering 200gm force on right side and 3/16" on left side that would close remaining space and also help to correct midline. Patient was advised to change elastics every 12 hours. Lower fixed appliance (0.022" x 0.028" slot) with MBT prescription was bonded and alignment was started with 0.016" NiTi wire (figure no. 3).

0.019"x0.025" SS was placed in lower arch after alignment and leveling and remaining spaces were closed in upper and lower arch by using class II intermaxillary elastics to correct canine and molar relation. After 15 months of treatment, 0.016" Niti wire was inserted in upper arch and vertical settling elastics are given.

In 17th month, molar bands were removed in upper arch and upper wire is cut distal to incisors. Settling of upper and lower arches was done by using settling elastics.

The case was debonded after 1.5 years of active orthodontic treatment. As retention protocol, upper and lower fixed multistranded wire retainer was bonded lingually on teeth extending from canine on one side to

Figure 1. Pretreatment Extra-oral and Intraoral Photographs

Figure 2. Pre-treatment Radiographs

Figure 3. Treatment Progress Photographs

opposite canine (figure no. 5). Lower arch aligned and remaining spaces in upper arch were closed by class I elastics from kobayashi hook on laterals to the hooks of first molar bands.

TREATMENT RESULTS

Crowding was successfully relieved in upper arch. Overjet was reduced at the end of treatment due to retraction of upper incisors. As both overbite and overjet were acceptable at the end of treatment, prognosis for stability was good (figure no. 5). Dental centerlines at end of treatment coincide with each other and to facial midline. The final anterior occlusal fit was good. Posteriorly, class I molar relationship was maintained on

both sides. Buccal segment interdigitation was reasonable and further settling is anticipated. The lower incisors inclination was maintained and space gained by extraction was utilized to relieve crowding, level curve of spee.

SKELETAL

SNA and SNB value was increased but there was no change in ANB angle. Wits appraisal increased by 3mm under the influence of occlusal plane leveling. SN-Mand angle and MMA show decrease of 1° while face height ratio show an increase of 1% due to rotation of mandibular plane upwards (figure no. 4, table no. 1).

DENTAL

The upper incisor to maxillary plane angle decreased by 12° to 106° following retraction of upper labial segment. The lower incisor to mandibular plane angle remained

unchanged during treatment. As a result of these changes, the interincisal angle was increased by 27° to 140°.

Figure 4. Post-treatment Radiographs

Table 1: Lateral Cephalometric Measurement

VARIABLE	NORMAL	PRE TREATMENT	POST TREATMENT	CHANGE
SNA	82° ± 3	77°	79°	2°
SNB	79° ± 3	72°	74°	2°
ANB	3° ± 1	5°	5°	0°
SN to mandible plane	32° ± 4	40°	39°	-1°
SN to maxillary plane	8° ± 3	11°	10°	-1°
Wits appraisal	0 mm	0mm	3 mm	+3 mm
Upperincisorto maxillary plane angle	108° ± 5	118°	106°	12°
Lowerincisorto mandibular plane angle	92° ± 5	99°	99°	0°
Interincisal angle	133° ± 10	113°	140°	27°
MMA angle	27° ± 5	29°	28°	-1°
Upper anterior face height		51 mm	51mm	0 mm
Lower anterior face height		59 mm	59.5 mm	+0.5 mm
Face height ratio	55%	59%	60%	1%
Lower incisor to APo line	0-2 mm	+4 mm	+3 mm	-1 mm
E-Centroid	0-2 mm	1 mm	+1.5 mm	+0.5 mm
Upper lip to Ricketts E Plane	-4mm	-0.5mm	-1.5mm	-1mm
Lower lip to Ricketts E Plane	-2 mm	2 mm	0 mm	0 mm
Nasolabial Angle	102° ± 8°	82°	97°	15°

Figure 5. End of Active Treatment Extra-oral and intra-oral Photographs

SOFT TISSUES

The nasiolabial angle increased by 15° due to retroclination of upper incisors during treatment and also due to soft tissue growth changes. Upper lip position relative to Ricketts E plane was reduced by 1mm and lower lip position was reduced by 2mm due to change in inclination of upper incisors.

DISCUSSION

In conventional driftodontics technique no space maintainer is given in mandibular arch as two third of the extraction space is utilized by canine and incisors. In present case as molar relations were class I at the start of treatment and nance palatal button was given in maxillary arch, a change in molar relation was undesirable and mandibular space maintainer was given to prevent anchorage loss at start of treatment. Mandibular arch was aligned by driftodontics in 8 months. It has been purposed that most effective driftodontics occur 6 months after extraction and need for fixed appliance should be evaluated between 6-9 months.³ An anchorage burn of 3mm was reported in present case. This anchorage burn was done once the incisor and canine class I relations were attained. Superimposition of pretreatment and posttreatment lateral cephalogram showed retraction of upper incisors in range of 4mm and 3mm mesial movement of molars. It is believed that mandibular plane angle tends to decrease in extraction treatment due counter wedge effects.⁶ Mandibular plane angle in present case is decreased by 1° during treatment.

Papandreas showed that mandibular plane angle decreases by 0.3° per year in extraction cases done with driftodontics.¹ No significant changes in facial proportions were noted after treatment. These outcome of treatment are consistent with studies done on facial

proportion after extraction treatment.⁶ As the change in mandibular plane angle was very small no adverse effects on overbite was noted. Increased overbite was managed by placing lower incisor brackets more incisal at the time of bonding.

No enamel decalcification and any visible sign of root resorption were noted in lower incisors. The overall treatment time was 16 months which is less than the average time for all first premolar extraction case takes. These favorable outcomes of treatment were in consistence with purposed benefit of driftodontics purposed in many studies.^{1,3}

CONCLUSION

A young female was treated with driftodontics. Relief of lower crowding was done by physiological drift of teeth. Less relapse is anticipated in lower incisor position as no traction force was applied.

REFERENCES

1. Papandreas SG, Buschang PH, Alexander RG, Kennedy DB, Koyama I. Physiologic drift of the mandibular dentition following first premolar extractions. *Angle Orthod.* 1993;63(2):127-34
2. Alexander RG. *The 20 principles of the Alexander discipline*: Quintessence Publishing; 2008.
3. Bourdet B. *Recherches et observations sur toutes les parties de l'art du dentiste*: JT Hérissant; 1757.
4. Miyajima K, Nakamura S. Distalization with 'driftodontics'. *J Clin Orthod.* 1994;28(7):393-4

5. Borzabadi-Farahani A, Borzabadi-Farahani A, Eslamipour F. Malocclusion and occlusal traits in an urban Iranian population. An epidemiological study of 11- to 14-year-old children. *Eur J Orthod.* 2009;31(5):477-84.
 6. Zafarmand AH, Zafarmand MM. Premolar extraction in orthodontics: Does it have any effect on patient's facial height? *J Int Soc Prev Community Dent.* 2015; 5(1):64-8.
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